

Moreno, C., Sáez, R., González, F., Almodóvar, G., Toscano, M., Playford, G., Alansari, A., Rziki, S., Bajddi, A. (2008). Age and depositional environment of the Draa Sfar massive sulphide deposit, Morocco. *Mineralium Deposita* 43, 891-911

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Abstract:

The Draa Sfar mineralization consists of two main stratabound orebodies, Sidi M'Barek and Tzacourt, located north and south of the Tensift River ("Oued Tessift"), respectively. Each orebody is comprised by at least two massive sulfide lenses. The hosting rocks are predominantly black shales, although minor rhyolitic rocks are also present in the footwall to the southern orebody. Shales, rhyolitic volcanic rocks, and massive sulfides are all included into the Sarhlef Series, which is recognized as one of the main stratigraphic units of the Moroccan Variscan Meseta. Hydrothermal activity related with an anomalous thermal gradient, together with a high sedimentation rate in a tectonically driven pull-apart marine basin, favored the accumulation of organic-rich mud in the deepest parts of the basin and the sedimentary environment suitable for massive sulfide deposition and preservation. This took place by replacement of the hosting unlithified wet mud below the sediment–water interface. Geochemical data suggest a sedimentary environment characterized by oxic water column and anoxic sediment pile with the redox boundary below the sediment–water interface. The low oxygen availability within the sediment pile inhibited oxidation and pyritization of pyrrhotite. Biostratigraphic analysis, based on the palynological content of the hosting black shales, restricts the age of the sulfides to the Asbian substage (mid-Mississippian). This age is consistent with earlier geochronological constraints.

Key words:

Draa Sfar, Massive sulfide deposits, Black shales, Biostratigraphy, Morocco